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Review Article

The Role of Microbiome, Sebum and Natural Remedies in Dandruff Management

Dr. Induru Jagadeesh*, Anusha T., A. Anitha, Ayesha Tabassum

Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy Bachupally Hyderabad-50090. India.

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ABSTRACT

Dandruff is a complex issue that is impacted by a variety of factors, including individual susceptibility, sebum production, scalp physiology, and microbiological and non-microbial factors. The complex interactions among sebaceous secretions, the scalp microbiota, and environmental factors that lead to the development of dandruff have been examined in this review. Although the function of *Malassezia* species has been thoroughly investigated, recent studies have shown that bacterial populations such as *Staphylococcus epidermidis* can exacerbate the illness. This improved knowledge of the scalp's microbial ecology opens the door to more potent therapeutic approaches that go beyond standard antifungal medications. Traditional herbal therapies for dandruff have given way to contemporary shampoos made with chemicals throughout time. However, there is a resurgence of interest in herbal and microbiome-friendly remedies because of growing worries about antimicrobial resistance and scalp irritation brought on by artificial components. Natural active ingredients with strong antifungal and anti-inflammatory qualities, such as neem, tea tree oil, amla, and tulsi, present a viable substitute for shampoos made of chemicals. In nutshell, the science of scalp for treatment of dandruff with herbal remedies was elaborated in this article.

INTRODUCTION

Dandruff is a common scalp condition marked by the build-up of corneocytes. These are skin cells that tend to stick together and form visible white or yellowish flakes.[1] These flakes can cause noticeable itching and discomfort. While dandruff is a long-lasting issue, it's generally non-

inflammatory and hence doesn't typically cause redness or swelling. [2] But there is clear need to bother this tissue as the scalp is one of the most sensitive areas of our skin and easily affected by such conditions. A significant component of the human body's overall attractiveness is hair. The hairs on one's head are linked to social distinction and beauty. The process of washing hair has

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Induru Jagadeesh

Address: Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy Bachupally Hyderabad-50090. India.

Email : jagadeesh8002@grcp.ac.in

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received relatively little attention, despite the fact that it has been cut, sculpted, and even coloured from the beginning of time.

Scalp Physiology: The Foundations of Dandruff Formation

The scalp is characterized by a thick layer of skin, a high concentration of hair follicles, and numerous sebaceous glands, all of which are supported by a rich network of blood vessels. In comparison to other areas of the skin, it has a poorer barrier function and is therefore less effective in preserving and rehydrating. Unfortunately, the scalp's great sensitivity makes it a breeding ground for a variety of skin issues, such as seborrheic dermatitis, dandruff, and other parasite infections. Like other skin, the scalp sheds dead cells. About once every month, the skin on the scalp regenerates. It's typical to have some dead skin peeling; after shampooing, 487,000 cells/cm² are discharged. This rate increases to cause dandruff. These are collections of corneocytes that separate from the stratum corneum's surface while maintaining a high degree of cohesiveness among themselves. [3, 4].

History Of Hair Care and Dandruff Treatment

Dandruff has been the state for generations, Indian traditional hair treatment has utilized herbs like amla and reeta throughout the Indian subcontinent. Using the filtered extract, Sapindas were boiled with dried Indian gooseberry (amla) and a variety of other herbs to create a highly powerful early shampoo. According to ancient Indian literature, sapindas, also called soapberries or soapsuds, are a tropical tree that grows widely throughout India. The fruit pulp of this tree contains saponins, which are a naturally occurring surfactant. In Indian scriptures, the lather produced by soapberry extract is referred to as phenakite. It leaves the hair manageable, lustrous, and silky. Other traditional

ingredients used for cleansing the hair included Shikakai (*Acacia cincinnal*), hibiscus flowers, rather (*Sapindas mokoros*), and Acapu (*Albizzia amara*), all known for their natural cleansing and nourishing properties.[5].

Microbial And Non-Microbial Factors Behind Dandruff

It has been noted that dandruff generally appears between puberty and middle age, when sebaceous gland activity is at its peak. [6] Individual differences in susceptibility determine the aetiology of dandruff. The causes can be divided into two categories: microbial and non-microbial.

a) Microbiological Elements:

1. Fungal: The most common cause of dandruff is thought to be *Malassezia furfur*. Dandruff can be caused by the fungus *Malassezia* through one or both of the following mechanisms: The scalp's Lipase enzyme is stimulated by *Malassezia*. The enzyme produces unsaturated and saturated fatty acids by oxidizing sebum triglycerides. Fungi rely on saturated fatty acids as a source of energy to grow and multiply. Arachidonic acid and oleic acid are examples of unsaturated fatty acids. Arachidonic acid plays a role in intensifying inflammatory reactions, whereas oleic acid irritates human skin. As these fatty acids break down, they can trigger fungal growth, along with inflammation and irritation of the scalp. These also result in dandruff, which are dry flakes. Altering the regular shedding of dead skin cells is the other way that this fungus creates dandruff. A small number of scalp enzymes break down connections between dead skin cells so that each one can be shed separately. Corneocytes are shedding off in clusters to produce apparent white flakes.[6]

2. Bacterial: The percentage of the two primary bacterial communities on the scalp is out of balance. Dandruff may also be caused by

Staphylococcus epidermidis and Propionibacterium acnes. [7, 8] Fig. 1 depicts the flowchart that shows the microbial causes of dandruff.

Fig-1: Flowchart showing the microbial causes of dandruff

b) Non-microbial Elements

The following factors that account for non-microbial causes for dandruff.

1. Damage to the outermost layer of the scalp, the stratum corneum.
2. Individual oleic acid susceptibility.
3. Dry scalp.
4. Skin that is greasy or itchy.
5. Dirt buildup as a result of infrequent shampooing.
6. Hair cosmetic sensitivity.
7. Additional scalp disorders such as eczema and psoriasis.[6]

Dandruff classification:

There are two primary forms of dandruff based on the symptoms:

A. Dry Dandruff B. Oily Dandruff

A) Dry Dandruff: Another name for it is pityriasis simplex, which is characterized by an overabundance of microscopic scales that build up on the scalp. There isn't a lot of hair loss from this kind of dandruff. There is no sign of skin inflammation in this form. The scales initially appear in the centre of the scalp before spreading to the frontal, parietal, and occipital regions.

B) Oily Dandruff: Pityriasis steatoides is the clinical term for oily dandruff. It might result from the production of sebum on the scalp. It could happen during adolescence. The scalp may be inflamed and have oily, filthy, yellow scales. This kind of dandruff is most frequently found on the head, behind the ears, across the breast bone, and

under the arms. [9]. The the major differences between these two dandruffs are listed in table 1.

Table 1: Difference between dry and oily dandruff:

Features	Dry dandruff	Oily dandruff
Appearance	Small, white, dry flakes	Larger yellowish, greasy flakes
Scalp type	Dry, lacks moisture	Oily, excess sebum production
Itching	Mild to moderate	More intense due to inflammation
Cause	Lack of scalp hydration, cold weather	Excess sebum, fungal growth (Malassezia)
Common areas	Found all over the scalp	Stick to scalp, mostly near hair roots
Hair condition	Hair looks dry and brittle	Hair appears greasy and sticky
Treatment	Hydrating shampoos, oils	Antifungal, sebum-controlling shampoos

Sebum And Scalp Health: A Double-Edged Sword

One of the most sensitive parts of the human skin is the scalp. It is distinguished by a thick layer of skin with high follicular density and a profusion of sebaceous glands, and it is rich in blood vessels. [10]. There is a substantial temporal link between

sebaceous gland activity and the involvement of sebum in dandruff. This comprises a rise in adolescence and early adulthood, a fall later in life, a low incidence from childhood to puberty, and an enhanced incidence during infancy (cradle cap). The figure 2 shows the linkage of these factors with dandruff formation.

Fig. 2: The Figure to Enlighten the Linkage of Dandruff to Sebum Level In Life Span.

Dandruff typically occurs only in areas of the skin with high sebum production. Triglycerides, fatty acids, sterol esters, cholesterol esters, wax esters, and squalene are all complex components of human sebum. Microbes break down the triglycerides and esters that make up sebum into monoglycerides, diglycerides, and free fatty acids.

The irritating reaction, which contributes to scalp hyperproliferation, is triggered in part by free fatty acids. Dandruff is strongly related to stress and hormones, which also affect the function of sebum secretion. [11,12] The role of microbes in dandruff: *Malassezia furfur* is the main cause of dandruff and grows best when fed the saturated

fatty acids found in sebum. This makes an oily scalp the perfect environment for fungal growth. When *Malassezia* grows too quickly, it disrupts the natural renewal of skin cells. Therefore, anti-fungal substances that target the elimination of *Malassezia* that causes cellular toxicity of the fungal cells are the main focus of contemporary dandruff treatments. [13] The Unilever study team used a novel technique known as next-generation sequencing (NGS) to conduct a thorough genetic analysis of the scalp microbiome. Over 100 individuals with both healthy and dandruff-prone scalps participated in the test; all had abstained from using anti-dandruff shampoo for six months. According to research, the amount of *Malassezia* on a dandruff-prone scalp is ten times more than that of a healthy scalp. However, the study also revealed information about the bacterial origins of dandruff in addition to the fungal ones. A qPCR method was used to precisely count the microorganisms. According to the study, scalps with dandruff had 100 times more *Staphylococcus capitis* germs. The study came to the conclusion that dandruff is caused by more than just *Malassezia*. The development and worsening of dandruff are influenced by the presence of both bacteria and fungi. [14]

Treatment Strategies for Dandruff

Shampoo: The word "shampoo" originally meant "to massage" and was first used in English in 1762. The name comes from Anglo-Indian shampoo, which is taken from the Hindi word champoo, which means champna, which means to smear, knead, or massage muscles. [15] Shampoos are defined as liquid, solid, or powdered surfactant formulations that efficiently remove skin debris and surface grease from hair. Nowadays, using a range of shampoos to wash one's hair and scalp has become a common and almost universal habit worldwide. The most popular hair care product on the market today is

shampoo, which is created with both synthetic and herbal ingredients [16]. Under the given circumstances, these surface-active chemicals are utilized to remove dirt, surface oil, and skin debris from the scalp and hair shaft without harming the skin, hair, or scalp. Traditional soap cakes have given way to the increasingly popular shampoos in the history of hair care. The preference for high-foam shampoos frequently leads to very dry hair, even if a good wash produces a lot of foam regardless of the kind of water or the type of pollutants. In these situations, proper hair conditioning becomes essential. Acne and psoriasis can also result from seborrhea, which is the abnormal release of sebum from sebaceous glands.

Herbal Shampoo: "Herbal shampoos are shampoos that are used to clean hair and contain natural ingredients." These shampoos have no negative side effects and are mostly used to remove dandruff, oils, filth, and contaminants from the environment [17].

Ideal shampoo qualities: The shampoo formulas of today go beyond simply cleaning the hair. Additional advantages like conditioning, surface smoothing, increased compatibility, and improved leather creaminess are anticipated.

1. It should thoroughly and successfully remove dirt, dust, excess sebum, and other fatty materials from the hair.
2. It should be able to generate a sufficient amount of foam to meet the user's psychological needs.
3. Rinsing with water should remove it simply and thoroughly.
4. After washing, the hair should be silky, shiny, and not completely dry.
5. It needs to give the hair a pleasing scent.
6. It shouldn't cause eye or skin irritation.

7. It needs to be gentle on the hands.
8. It should provide the ideal amount of foam to meet the user's psychological needs.
9. If accidentally spilled, it shouldn't harm the eye's tissues [18]. Herbal shampoos are made from ancient medical plants and have two functions: they clean hair and keep the scalp free of dandruff. These compositions are designed to remove dandruff, oil, grime, and contaminants from the environment. [19]

The Shift Towards Herbal Based Anti-Dandruff Solutions

Serious issues with the hair and scalp can result from synthetic compounds [20]. The rise in azoles-resistant strains of *Malassezia* species makes antimicrobial resistance one of the major public health issues in the treatment of Scalp disorders (SD) [21]. Herbal medications or their mixtures are a good substitute for pharmaceuticals. The usage of natural products in cosmetics has dramatically increased during the last few decades. There are a lot of herbal shampoos on the market now that include plant extracts and essential oils, among other herbal ingredients. Numerous plants are frequently utilized in shampoos and are said to have positive benefits on hair type. [15] In order to prevent and treat SD, natural shampoo that contains an efficient plant-based ingredient for appropriate scalp treatment may be advantageous for both the health and appearance of the scalp. Essential oils and plant extracts are examples of plant-based substances with complete compositions, a variety of qualities, a range of actions, and a minimal potential for irritation. It was observed that the synergistic combination of 1,8-cineole (eucalyptol), (-)- α -bisabolol, and *Melaleuca alternifolia* (*M. alternifolia*) leaf oil in a 1:1:1 ratio had demonstrated therapeutic antibacterial ability against pathogenic microflora related to SD. In order to create a base that only produces specific cosmetics, herbal cosmetics are

made with a range of permissible cosmetic ingredients, including one or more botanical substances. Customers now prefer herbal-based cosmetics over synthetic ones due to the high percentage of dangerous ingredients in health cosmetics. [22]

Effectivity Of Natural Actives in Anti-Dandruff Treatment

Although herbal extracts such as tea tree oil, rosemary oil, coleus oil, clove oil, pepper extract, neem, and basil typically require higher concentrations to be effective compared to synthetic compounds, they still possess notable anti-*Pityrosporum* properties. Individually or in combination, these components can be used to their full potential in anti-dandruff shampoos. In both minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) tests, commercial shampoos containing tea tree oil, rosemary oil, henna, and lemon do not outperform shampoos with synthetic chemicals, while having good anti-*pityrosporum* action in vitro. However, shampoos containing herbal anti-dandruff compounds might be adequate for frequent use.[23] In addition herbal active usage has very few negative effects. [24]

Natural Actives in Anti-Dandruff Formulations

A good substitute for synthetic formulations are herbal active ingredients or their derivatives. Numerous phytochemical substances with effective antifungal properties, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, etc., are found in plant products. These substances can be combined with other polyherbal mixes to help manage dandruff. To achieve the intended impact, natural botanicals might be employed in their unrefined form, as derivatives, or as purified extracts. Numerous plants have been included in hair and scalp care formulations due to reports of their

positive effects on the hair and scalp. Since flavonoids are present in the leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* (tulsi) and *Azadirachta indica* (neem), the ethanolic extract of these plants has strong antibacterial activity and is safe, effective, and reasonably priced. According to published data, neem extract concentrations of 50% and more have the best level of dandruff growth suppression. [25] and that of Tulsi extract demonstrated antidandruff efficacy at concentrations of 2% and higher. [26] Many plant extracts, such as *Glycine max* (soybean), *Rosmarinus officinalis* (rosemary), *Arctium lappa* (burdock), *Zingiber officinalis* (ginger), *Salvia officinalis* (sage), *Mentha piperata* (mint), *Plantago major* (greater plantain), *Melaleuca spp.* (tea tree), *Camellia chinensis* (tea), *Thymus vulgaris* (thyme), and *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (yashtimadhu) are among the herbal extracts used to make antidandruff shampoos and oils. The chemical compounds gallic acid and ethyl gallate found in *Terminalia bellerica* (baheda) fruits are responsible for the fruit extracts' inhibitory effect. [26] Beta-sitosterol, gallic acid, ellagic acid, gallate, galloyl glucose, and chebulagic acid are among the tannins found in *Terminalia chebula* (haritaki). [27, 28] *Terminalia bellerica* dry fruit extracts, both crude and methanolic, have a wide range of antibacterial activity. Tea tree oil is known to have strong antifungal properties among the natural components. The Australian *Melaleuca alternifolia* leaves yield tea tree oil, an essential oil. It is a blend of terpenes and hydrocarbons, with about 100 distinct compounds in varying amounts. Terpinen-4-ol, the main active ingredient in tea tree oil, is widely recognized for its strong antibacterial properties. For the treatment of dandruff, concentrations of 0.25% to 5% tea tree oil seem to be both efficient and well-tolerated. For dandruff sufferers who would rather use a natural solution and are prepared to shampoo their hair every day, tea tree oil is a good substitute. [29,

30]. In addition to its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic qualities, henna (*Lawsonia inermis*) exhibits potent fungicidal effects. This plant extract's chemical components include flavonoids, beta-sitosterol, quinoids, naphthalene derivatives, and gallic acid. [31] It also works wonders as a hair conditioner. *Malassezia furfur* was completely inhibited by the chloroformic extract of henna, according to a study on the antifungal effects of methanolic, aqueous, and chloroform extracts of henna leaves. [32,33] For a study, plant extracts were prepared from *Citrus limon* (lemon), *Emblica officinalis* (amla), *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek), *Vitis vinifera* (grapevine), *Papaver somniferum* (poppy), and *Allium cepa* (onion) in different concentrations to assess their effects on inhibiting the growth of *M. furfur*. The wells of plates inoculated with *Malassezia furfur* were filled with the aqueous plant extracts. *Citrus limon* extract had the largest zone of inhibition compared to other plant extracts, while extracts from *Papaver somniferum* and *Allium cepa* did not exhibit any inhibition zone, according to the results. [34] Flavonoids are present in significant concentrations in *Ocimum sanctum*. Fatty acids, such as stearic, palmitic, oleic, and linoleic acid, are the main components of *Ocimum sanctum*. It functions as a microbiological agent and exhibits strong anti-inflammatory properties against arachidonic acid, leukotriene, and prostaglandin. The largest zone of inhibition was generated by a 100% neem leaf extract. Additionally, it can treat ringworm infections, psoriasis, acne, and dandruff, among other epidermal skin conditions. [35] Bhringraj powder had outstanding antifungal properties. Bhringraj Powder was used as one of the primary antidandruff components in a shampoo formulation. [36] Dandruff on the scalp may be effectively treated using herbal anti-dandruff hair shampoo that contains tea tree oil, aloe vera gel, and sodium

lauryl sulfate. In addition to being safer than chemical dandruff removers, the shampoos' formulations may significantly lessen hair loss when combing and promote hair growth. [37] Because herbal cosmetics are thought to be safe and side effect-free, there is a growing demand for and knowledge of them.

Scalp Microbiome: A Revolutionary Approach to Dandruff Control

The scalp microbiome is the balance of the microbial population on the scalp, which consists of the totality of all microorganisms that inhibit bacteria, viruses, and fungus. According to international research, the scalp microbiome is dominated by *Cutibacterium acnes*, *Staphylococcus epidermis*, and *Malassezia spp.* and has a relatively low bacterial diversity when compared to other body regions. [38] The scalp produces a lot of vitamin-rich sebum and is humid, which leads to the growth of cutaneous bacteria, pathogens, biofilm, and microorganisms that are unique to the scalp. Dandruff is also caused by an imbalance in the percentage of the two primary bacterial populations on the scalp, *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. [39] In order to combat dandruff and other scalp-related problems, many new products focus on rebalancing the scalp microbiome. These products contain ingredients that nourish the scalp, restore the microbiome's equilibrium, and reduce the itching that comes with dandruff. The skin microbiome, sometimes referred to as normal flora, is a diverse population of bacteria, fungi, and viruses [40]. These microbes lack the enzyme machinery required for the synthesis of fatty acids, particularly *Malassezia* yeast. As a result, they rely on external sources to meet their fatty acid needs. Several lipases, which are enzymes that may hydrolyze the triglycerides found in sebum, are secreted by *Malassezia* yeasts. Beneficial bacteria

that inhabit the epidermis and the upper regions of hair follicles are part of normal flora. The makeup and function of the scalp microbiome, a varied microbial ecology, are influenced by both internal and external factors. The scalp microbiota can be disturbed by extrinsic factors such as humidity, sun exposure, stress, dry skin, seborrheic dermatitis, and inappropriate cosmetic use. The scalp microbiome is also significantly shaped by intrinsic variables, such as immunosuppression, hormonal swings, genetic susceptibility to particular bacterial communities, and dietary abnormalities. Developing successful ways to preserve scalp health and prevent or treat dermatological problems requires an understanding of the intricate interactions between these extrinsic and internal variables and how they affect the scalp microbiome [41]. Consequently, a variety of undesirable scalp conditions, particularly dandruff and hair loss, can result from any imbalance between these microbes [42]. *Propionibacterium acnes* are microorganisms that are present on the scalp. Through a direct or indirect mode of action, coconut oil is widely used throughout the world to moisturize the skin, support healthy scalps, and repair damaged hair [43, 44]. According to supporting research, coconut oil and its main ingredient, lauric acid, have a more effective inhibitory effect on the growth and invasion of dermatophytes on the skin than other hair oils that are frequently used in India, like mustard oil, cantharidin oil, amla oil, etc. [45,46,47]. It has also been found to increase moisture retention and reduce transepidermal water loss (TEWL) when applied to the skin over a prolonged period, both of which may play an important role in shaping the scalp's microbiota. [48]. Therefore, it would appear plausible to hypothesize that applying coconut oil has a strong impact on the physiology of the scalp, which alters the scalp microbiota [49,50]. The Fig 3 shows the stages of microbial imbalance leading to dandruff

Fig 3: The Stages During Microbial Imbalance Leading to Dandruff

Comparison Of Healthy and Dandruff Scalp Microbiome

Consistent with findings from other populations around the world, *Propionibacterium acnes* was associated with a healthy scalp, while *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was more commonly linked to dandruff. These two bacteria also emerged as the dominant scalp colonizers in the Indian population. [51,52,53,54]. Therefore, it can be concluded that the ratio of *P. acnes* to *S. epidermidis* could serve as a key indicator for diagnosing and treating dandruff. A healthy scalp exhibited a lower ratio of *M. restricta* to *M. globosa*. Similar findings were observed in a Chinese study using the same sequencing

technique (Illumina MiSeq) [54]. The high prevalence of uncultured *Malassezia* sp. in the scalp microbiome demonstrated the different microbial diversity expected in the Indian population due to the intrinsic variety in ethnicity, climatic circumstances, nutrition, and other variables [55]. The fungal cell wall integrity and glycoprotein biosynthesis depend on the N-glycan biosynthesis pathway, which was found to be more abundant in the dandruff scalp. [56] When comparing the bacterial microbiome of a healthy scalp to that of a dandruff-prone scalp, a notable enrichment of the production and metabolism pathways of vitamins and cofactors was found. Numerous amino acids and vitamins, including

biotin, are said to be helpful in preventing dandruff and promoting healthy hair and scalp. [57,58] Microbiome composition of a healthy scalp to that

of a dandruff-prone scalp as shown in fig.4. The prominent herbs that balance the scalp microbes were listed in table 2.

Fig 4: The Composition of Microbial Flora in Healthy Scalp and Scalp with Dandruff

Table 2: The benefits on scalp by herbs with their family

Herb	Family and origin	Active components	Benefits on scalp	Reference
Acacia concinna (Shikakai)	Fabaceae.	Antibacterial, Antifungal, Saponins	Antimicrobial activity against bacteria and fungi; controls scalp infections, prevents dandruff.	[59, 60,61,62]
Camellia oleifera	Theaceae.	Oleic acid (78%), Palmitic acid (10%), Linoleic acid (9%)	Moisturizes hair, promotes moisture retention, restores healthy hair properties, reduces frizz.	[63, 64, 65, 66]
Azadirachta indica (Neem)	Meliaceae .	Azadirachtin, nimbin, fatty acids	Anti-dandruff; antifungal properties, effective against Malassezia sp. and head lice.	[67, 68, 69]
Emblica officinalis (Amla)	Phyllanthaceae	Vitamin C, Tannins, Polyphenols	Promotes hair growth, strengthens hair, exhibits anti-dandruff and antifungal activity, prevents hair loss.	[70, 71, 72,73]
Sapindus mukorossi (Reetha)	Sapindaceae	Saponins, Triterpenoid saponins	Natural surfactant, anti-dandruff, reduces yeast on scalp, antifungal activity.	[74, 75, 76]

Garcinia mangostana (Mangosteen)	Guttiferae.	α -Mangostin (69%), Xanthones	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antifungal; promotes hair rejuvenation and growth.	[77, 78]
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Future Prospects:

Natural remedies that improve scalp and hair health while maintaining the delicate balance of the microbiome are becoming more and more popular as research shows the connections between microbiome imbalances and skin/scalp problems.

Microbiome-Based Anti-Dandruff Solutions

Preventing scalp conditions like seborrheic dermatitis and dandruff requires maintaining a healthy scalp microbiota. Enhancing moisture, regulating sebum production, avoiding oxidative stress, and preserving the scalp's natural pH are the goals of these therapies. Crucially, these products support a healthy microbiota while assisting in the reduction of symptoms such as sensitivity, redness, flakiness, and excessive sebum production [79, 80, 81].

Scalp Microbiome Exfoliating Mask: (Detox)

Overproduction of sebum on the scalp creates an ideal habitat for the growth of lipophilic bacteria like *Malassezia*. A surplus of *Malassezia* species can cause seborrheic dermatitis and dandruff, even though they are normally found on healthy scalps. Therefore, it is essential to control sebum production without eliminating these microorganisms in order to preserve a healthy scalp environment [82,83,84,85].

Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), a harsh chemical that can dry out the scalp and disturb the microbiota, is used in certain commercial products to balance sebum production. Natural alternatives, such as jojoba ester beads, act as biodegradable

mechanical exfoliants, gently removing dead skin cells from the scalp and promoting a healthier scalp environment. Sarcosine, a derivative of amino acids, also decreases sebum production, which limits the amount of "food" that lipophilic bacteria may consume. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that sarcosine gradually increases the diversity of microorganisms on the scalp, promoting a more wholesome microbiome. Antioxidant-rich Australian wild berries shield the scalp from oxidative stress (ROS), which is brought on by the growth of *Malassezia* species.[86]

Cleansing Shampoos for Microbiome Preservation: (Purify)

Shampoos and other cleaning solutions are essential for maintaining the microbial community on the scalp. Shampoos that contain microbiome-safe components can assist cleanse the scalp without causing damage to the skin barrier or depleting it of its natural oils. Healthy hair development depends on a healthy scalp environment, which is restored and maintained with this method. [87,88]

Yeast-fermented, lipid-based bio surfactants are examples of naturally occurring substances that can gently wash the scalp without altering its microbiome. The antioxidants found in Australian wild berries help protect the scalp and hair follicles from environmental damage. Amino acids found in vegan proteins enter the hair shaft and create a barrier that protects the scalp and hair. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that

prebiotics such as alpha-glucan oligosaccharide promote the development of a healthy microbiome and promote a balanced microbial environment throughout the cleansing process.[86]

Scalp Essence for Stress Relief: (Soothe)

The scalp must be nourished and shielded from possible stressors that could upset the microbiota and result in dryness, irritation, or flakiness after it has been cleansed. Because of the high sebum content, lipophilic bacteria predominate in the scalp microbiome. Incorporating prebiotics and post-biotics into scalp treatments can support the microbiome's general resilience and health by nourishing and preserving its diversity [89,90]. It has been demonstrated that ingredients like prickly pears and peach gum lessen the redness and flakiness of the scalp, while a zinc complex taken from smithsonite stone shields it from UVB rays. By keeping keratinocytes from glycolating, zinc also promotes the formation of collagen and maintains the general health of the scalp.[86]

Protective Conditioners: (Shield)

Conditioners help keep hair strands lubricated, which lessens the force required for combing and helps keep them from breaking or tangling. A number of naturally occurring substances are very good at protecting hair while maintaining the health of the scalp microbiota.

- To lessen porosity and restore damaged keratin fibers, arginine and fermented amino acids form bonds with amino acids and keratin fragments, including broken disulfide bonds.
- Because ximenynic acid is present, ximenia oil, which is high in fatty acids and vitamin C, has silicone-like qualities that lubricate hair, avoid dryness, and lessen irritation.
- Sea buckthorn strengthens and increases the suppleness of hair strands since it contains vitamins and fatty acids.

- Wheat proteins help stop hair breakage and improve mechanical resilience to chemical and physical stresses.

By decreasing breakage and enhancing overall strength, these substances promote hair health and help prevent damage to the hair. [86]

Factors Contributing To The Resurgence Of Herbal Remedies

It has long been thought that herbal treatments, which are made up of plant parts or unpurified plant extracts with a range of active ingredients, function in concert. There are a number of reasons for the recent spike in interest in and use of herbal therapies. These elements demonstrate how consumer preferences are shifting in favour of natural therapies and how there is growing confidence in the potential advantages of herbal remedies.

1. Claims of Efficacy: The public's interest in plant-based medications has grown as a result of several assertions about their effectiveness. These claims often emphasize the natural healing properties of plants.

2. Preference for Natural Therapies: Due to a growing interest in complementary and alternative medicine compared to traditional pharmaceutical treatments, consumers are showing a growing preference for natural therapies.

3. False Belief in Superiority: The idea that herbal products are better than manufactured or synthetic medications is common, but frequently incorrect. The preference for natural alternatives is fueled by this idea.

4. Dissatisfaction with Conventional Medicine: A lot of people turn to herbal therapies because they're unhappy with how conventional medications work. In situations where traditional

medications have failed, some people think herbal remedies could be useful.

5. Cost and Side consequences of contemporary

Drugs: People are drawn to herbal alternatives because they are thought to be less expensive and kinder to the body, as well as because of the high cost and possible negative consequences of contemporary drugs.

6. Quality and Safety Improvement:

Scientific and technological developments have greatly enhanced the efficacy, safety, and quality of herbal medications, increasing their appeal to consumers.

7. Medical Diagnosis Doubts:

Some patients believe that their doctors have misdiagnosed their health issues, which makes them think that herbal treatments are an additional effective therapy choice.

8. Movement Toward Self-Medication:

People are increasingly choosing to treat themselves with herbal medicines, frequently without a prescription from a doctor, as part of a growing trend toward self-medication. Using Herbal Medicines to Support the Body's Natural Healing Process
When considering the body's inherent ability to heal itself, herbal remedies become even more alluring. Herbal remedies are a popular choice for people looking for a more natural approach to health and wellbeing since they are thought to improve the body's inherent ability to heal itself given the correct circumstances and assistance. [91,92]

CONCLUSION

In the end, keeping a healthy scalp necessitates a multimodal strategy that incorporates microbial balance, balanced sebum production, and excellent hygiene habits. The move toward microbiome-supportive and herbal-based remedies is part of a

larger trend in dermatology that embraces the therapeutic power of nature while utilizing scientific discoveries. The future of dandruff treatment can shift from symptomatic alleviation to long-term scalp health and fitness by incorporating these discoveries. Prebiotic or probiotic formulations, mild cleansers, and scalp exfoliants may offer a comprehensive strategy for controlling dandruff while reducing side effects. Additionally, new developments in scalp care technologies, such as molecular diagnostics and next-generation sequencing, provide fresh perspectives on how to treat dandruff individually based on each person's unique scalp microbiome profile.

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